

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

GRAIN QUALITY

Grain grades in relation to seedling growth and productivity

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This study was designed to determine the relationship of 1,000-grain weight to seedling growth and productivity.

Spikelets of IET75737, IET7574, and IET7575 were sorted by immersing them in 1.0, 1.06, and 1.18 specific gravity solutions using 0, 90, and 270 g common salt/liter of water. Floating grains were categorized as partially filled, average, good, and very good. The graded grains were tested for germination and seedling growth in the nursery and for yield potential in the field.

Germination and seedling growth, influenced by seed size up to 10 d, compensated at 20-22 d after sowing (Table 1). As a result, crop productivity was not affected (Table 2).

Table 1. Germination and seedling growth in relation to grain grade. ^a Andhra Pradesh, India.

Grain grade	Germination (%)						Seedling growth (cm)					
	IET7573		IET7574		IET7575		IET7573		IET7574		IET7575	
	10 DAS	20 DAS	10 DAS	20 DAS	10 DAS	20 DAS	10 DAS	22 DAS	10 DAS	22 DAS	10 DAS	22 DAS
Partially filled	36	91	15	84	17	89	8.0	17.4	8.6	14.8	9.7	19.7
Average	59	93	21	85	31	89	8.5	17.4	8.7	14.8	10.2	19.7
Good	68	94	30	86	45	89	9.6	17.5	8.9	14.7	10.8	19.4
Very good	95	95	48	88	57	90	9.8	17.4	9.2	14.8	11.3	19.5

^a Av of 3 replications. DAS = days after sowing.

Table 2. Yield in relation to grain grade. Andhra Pradesh, India.

Grain grade	Yield (t/ha)		
	IET7573	IET7574	IET7575
Partially filled	3.6	3.8	3.8
Average	3.4	4.0	3.8
Good	3.7	4.4	4.0
Very good	3.7	4.1	4.0
CD (0.05)	V = NS T = NS V in T = NS T in V = NS		V = 11.7% T = 10.6%

Because consumer preference is mainly for size and shape of the whole kernel, fully filled grain may be used

for consumption, rather than for seed. □

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DISEASE RESISTANCE

Susceptibility of rice hybrids to blast (BI)

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We studied the susceptibility of six F₁ hybrids to BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cavara during navarai (Dec-Jan to Mar-Apr 1983-84). TKM9 was the base parent, crossed with Co 29 (resistant), IR36 (moderately resistant), and IR50 (highly susceptible). The Uniform Blast

Susceptibility of rice hybrids to BI. Tamil Nadu, India.

Cross	BI	Disease intensity ^a			Heterosis ^b (%)
		F ₁ hybrid (av)	Ovule parent (av)	Pollen parent (av)	
TKM9/Co 29	Leaf	5.4	4.8	2.6	45.95**
	Neck	2.5	3.3	1.2	11.11
Co 29/TKM9	Leaf	4.2	2.6	4.8	13.51
	Neck	2.5	1.2	3.4	8.70
TKM9/IR36	Leaf	4.4	4.8	3.6	4.76
	Neck	2.3	3.3	1.5	-4.17
IR36/TKM9	Leaf	3.8	3.6	4.8	-9.52
	Neck	2.1	1.5	3.3	-12.50
TKM9/IR50	Leaf	4.6	4.8	6.6	-19.30*
	Neck	1.3	3.3	5.2	-69.41**
IR50/TKM9	Leaf	3.4	6.6	4.8	-40.35**
	Neck	0.3	5.2	3.3	-92.94**

^a By SES. ^b Significant at 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.